

Variation of the Cataphoretic Velocity of Colloidal Particles during Aggregation. Part I.

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The cataphoretic velocity of colloidal particles often shows a minimum, followed by a continuous increase as the concentration of a uni-univalent electrolyte added to a colloidal solution increases (Mukherjee and Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **2**, 296; Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Roychoudhury, *ibid.*, 1927, **4**, 493; Mukherjee, Roychoudhury and their co-workers, *ibid.*, 1928, **5**, 697, 735). Near about the stage of appearance of visible aggregates and the breaking up of the colloidal solution into a precipitated mass, a sudden fall of the cataphoretic velocity takes place (Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Roychoudhury, *loc. cit.*). It has been suggested (Mukherjee *et al*, *loc. cit.*, *cf.* also Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Ghosh, *Trans. National Inst. Sci. India*, 1935, **1**, 47), that the increase in the cataphoretic speed near about coagulating concentrations is a direct consequence of the aggregation of the colloidal particles. It was also suggested that even at the high concentrations of uni-univalent electrolytes, which are used, the primary adsorption of similarly charged ions is not likely to be so preponderant over the electrical adsorption of oppositely charged ions, as to increase the cataphoretic velocity to the extent which has been actually observed.

These observations and suggestions have an important bearing on the theories of cataphoresis and of the electrical double layer. In recent years, the dependence of the cataphoretic velocity on the size and shape of a colloidal particle has been investigated both theoretically and experimentally by Freundlich and Abramsohn (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, **128**, 25; 1928, **133**, 57), Abramsohn, (*J. Gen. Physiol*, 1929, **12**, 711; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, **35**, 291) and Mooney (*Phys. Rev.*, 1924, **23**, 396; 1931, **35**, 331), Henry, (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1931, **A**, **133**, 106) and Bikermanu (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1934, **A**, **171**, 209).

The Debye and Hückel theory of strong electrolytes which is valid for very low ionic strengths, has in recent years often been drawn upon to formulate the dependence of the cataphoretic velocity on the

ionic strength of the colloidal solution (*cf.* Abramoohn, *loc. cit.*, Henry, *loc. cit.*).

In discussions on the above subjects, three aspects are generally ignored, these are (a) the interionic repulsions between the mobile ions in the double layer to which is to be attributed the stabilising influence of the electrical charge of the particle, (b) the effect of the aggregation on the distribution of ions in the double layer, (c) the special rôle of the adsorption of ions, and (d) the contribution of the colloidal particles to the ionic strength of the medium, an estimate of which involves a knowledge of the number and valency of the colloidal ions and of the mobile ions associated with them. These aspects also raise the more general question as to how far the Debye-Hückel concepts are valid for the peculiar distribution of electrical charges round colloidal particles (Mukherjee, *Kolloid Z.*, 1933, 62, 257; 1933, 63, 36; 1933, 65, 71; 1934, 67, 178). Investigations on the effect of the aggregation of colloidal particles on the cataphoretic velocity under conditions where the ionic strength may be assumed to be constant as a first approximation afford valuable information likely to throw considerable light on the whole subject. It will be seen from the sequel that concurrent with the process of aggregation in the region of slow coagulation, the cataphoretic velocity of the aggregates increases. There are also cases where a diminution has been observed and the sudden fall in the cataphoretic velocity near the stage of the precipitation of the colloid has been confirmed. It has been shown in this paper that the theories which ignore the aspects mentioned above are inadequate, and the relationships between cataphoretic velocity and size and shape of particles suggested in recent years are not valid and that detailed considerations of the distribution of ions in the double layer and their adsorption are necessary.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The best course to follow the effect of aggregation on the c.v. experimentally is to add a definite concentration of an electrolyte to a colloid which coagulates a particular sol in a time sufficient to permit the measurement of the c.v. during the progress of aggregation. For this, the micro-cataphoretic apparatus is more suitable than the U-tube method, though the latter method gave sufficient indications that such an effect exists (*cf.* Mukherjee, Roychoudhury and Biswas,

J. Indian Chem. Soc., 1931, **8**, 373). The micro-cataphoretic apparatus with reversible electrodes used by us is essentially the same as that of Northrop (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1922, **4**, 629) as modified by Freundlich and Abramsohn (*loc. cit.*) with the further modification that the main cell can be detached from the electrode vessels. The rectangular cell is fitted with *detachable* three-way stop-cocks, at either ends, which permit of ease of cleansing the different parts.

The cataphoretic velocity in cm/sec per volt/cm. is calculated from Smoluchowski's equation,

$$V = \frac{3}{4} V_{\frac{1}{6}} + \frac{1}{4} V_{\frac{1}{2}}$$

where $V_{\frac{1}{6}}$ and $V_{\frac{1}{2}}$ are the observed velocities of the particles at $\frac{1}{6}$ and $\frac{1}{2}$ height of the cell. Measurements of velocities at different heights of the cell show that the curve relating the velocity with different depths of the cell is approximately a parabola (*cf.* Fig. 1 and Table I), as required by theory. The numbers in the following tables give the c.v. multiplied by 10^5 .

TABLE I

Arsenious sulphide sol and potassium chloride.

Height	...	1/9	1/6	1/4	1/3	2/5	1/2	3/5	2/3		
$V^* \times 10^5$		46.7	51.4	54.16	54.54	50.55	47.83	—	—		
		$V = \frac{3}{4} V_{\frac{1}{6}} + \frac{1}{4} V_{\frac{1}{2}} = 50.51 \times 10^5$									
Height		0.05	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.35	0.4	0.45	0.5
$V^* \times 10^5$		39.36	44.5	51.69	51.69	53.64	53.04	50.41	47.35	50.41	47.65
		$V = \frac{3}{4} V_{\frac{1}{3}} + \frac{1}{4} V_{\frac{1}{2}} = 50.68 \times 10^5$									

* Velocity, V in cm/sec per volt/cm.

The reproducibility of the results is illustrated by the figures in Table I, and is within 1% when sufficient care is taken to cleanse the cell properly and the current is kept constant within 0.1 of a milliamp. Results given in Table II were taken without the precautions, stated above and though they were not concordant, it will be seen that the effect of time on c. v. of As_2S_3 sol in presence of potassium chloride is definitely marked.

TABLE II.

Preliminary results with arsenious sulphide sol and potassium chloride (N/6).

■ Time (counted since the colloid and electrolyte were mixed) during which the measurements were made.	$V \times 10^5$.		* Time (counted since the colloid and electrolyte were mixed) during which the measurements were made.	$V \times 10^5$.
7—23 min.	35.81 cm./sec. per volt/cm.	23.5 †	5—13 min.	49.58 cm./sec. per volt/cm.
35—45	50.94	23.40 ‡	40—51	55.33
55—65	52.0		75—83	56.18
85—115	52.5		4—15	35.2
200—210	52.3		34—90	38.66
220—230	50.7		120—135	42.24
5—13	55.31		5—25	42.85
35—51	61.53		75—87	49.41
72—85	60.52			
95—110	60.17			

In Tables III to VI, the effect of time and aggregation on the c. v. of particles of arsenious sulphide, palmitic acid, vanadium

■ In the above table the times given have the same significance.

† $V \times 10^5$ after coagulation.

‡ Velocity of the coagula thoroughly shaken with the supernatant liquid.

pentoxide, and tungstic acid sols have been given. The above sols were polydisperse and were of different grades of dispersion. The arsenious sulphide sols referred to in Tables I, II, III, IV and V were finely dispersed and with the magnification used (eye-piece, 28X, objective 20 mm.), the particles of the pure sol could rarely be seen under the microscope. As, however, the coagulation proceeds, the aggregates become visible. From the number of divisions of the micrometer eye-piece, with which the linear dimensions of the aggregates coincide and from the magnification, the size of the aggregates has been calculated. It is often observed that on the application of the electric field, the particles became visible though practically none were observed in its absence. It appears that under these conditions, the number of particles of sufficiently large size was very small and with the application of the field, the resulting cataphoresis brings into the field of observation more particles. Besides, the motion helps the visual observation. The size of the particles varied from 3.1μ downwards in the case of the pure sols, whereas in presence of electrolytes, the size varied from 3.1μ to 15.5μ .

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

 AS_2S_3 sol.

Curves 1-3 refer respectively to $N/7$ KCl, $N/300-BaCl_2$ and $N/300-AlCl_3$.
O means C. V. after coagulation.

The coagulating electrolytes were potassium chloride, barium chloride and aluminium chloride. The concentration of the electrolyte was so chosen that it took about 1-2 hours for coagulation to take place. Equal volumes of a sol and an electrolyte were taken in two beakers and mixed by pouring the electrolyte to the sol. The time of mixing was noted. Measurements were then taken during the process of coagulation at noted intervals of time. After a definite time for a particular concentration of electrolyte, the sol was seen to be partially coagulated. The supernatant solution was decanted off and the c_v of the particles in it measured.

Arsenious Sulphide Sol.

The arsenious sulphide sol has been prepared as described before (Mukherjee and Chaudhury, *loc. cit.*). Measurements were also taken by shaking the coagula with the supernatant suspension of the colloid after coagulation. These results have been collected together in Tables III and IV and the curves have been shown in Fig. 2.

TABLE III.

Electrolyte	Time after mixing	Before coagulation.			After coagulation		
		$V_{\frac{1}{4}}$	$V_{\frac{1}{2}}$	$V.$	$V_{\frac{1}{4}}$	$V_{\frac{1}{2}}$	$V.$
Water		27'24	45'00	31'55			
N/9-KCl	12-21 min.	36'56	51'95	40'42	31'1	47'56	35'2
	40-55	40'2	54'6	43'75			
	2-12	35'22	51'92	39'4			
	32-38	40'71	56'85	44'74			
	5-12	36'49	52'35	40'7			
	40'45	43'26	53'37	45'78			
	77-84	40'64	56'72	44'66			
	6-10	34'81	52'94	39'34			
	46-50	39'89	56'16	43'95			
	4-10	37'81	50'76	41'04			
36-44	39'75	58'43	44'39				

* Supernatant coagulated sol thoroughly shaken with the original precipitate and velocity measured.

TABLE III (contd.).

Electrolyte	Time after mixing	Before coagulation			After centrifuging		
		$V_{\frac{1}{2}}$	$V_{\frac{1}{4}}$	V	$V_{\frac{1}{2}}$	$V_{\frac{1}{4}}$	V
N-KCl	10-18 min	34.81	40.08	38.27			
	30-40	36.26	52.17	40.48			
	56-63	40.04	50.42	42.23			
	4-13	35.73	48.74	38.97	36.64	48.92	39.68
	68-74	38.98	55.2	43.02			
	5-11	35.47	48.83	39.78	36.72	49.74	39.95
	43-47	41.42	52.23	43.95			
	10-14	36.54	47.26	39.23			
	60-64	40.47	52.38	43.95	36.99	49.42	40.07
	5-8	36.41	49.04	39.56			
	13-18	36.53	49.66	39.8			
	25-30	37.78	50.32	40.9	36.4	49.2	39.6
	38-44	38.9	50.65	41.92			
	50-58	39.9	50.87	42.62			
64-72	40.8	51.9	43.6				
12-16	36.09	51.53	39.94				
21-28	37.15	50.63	40.33				
24 hrs	47.66	59.16	49.77	44.49	56.4	47.67	
24 hrs	14-28	35.52	53.63	40.04			
		46.65	60.15	50.01			

TABLE IV

Electrolyte	Time after mixing	Before coagulation			After coagulation		
		$V_{\frac{1}{2}}$	$V_{\frac{1}{4}}$	V	$V_{\frac{1}{2}}$	$V_{\frac{1}{4}}$	V
N/300-BaCl ₂	6-10 min	16.5	20.1	17.11	16.15	21.8	17.51
	52-58	20.21	23.66	21.06			
	3-10	16.53	20.7	17.53			
	25-31	18.13	22.57	19.23	16.35	21.74	17.67
	55-60	20.6	23.14	21.23			
60-85	21.19	24.44	21.98				
N/350-BaCl ₂	10-15 min	16.01	20.29	17.07			
	70-73	19.87	24.52	21.01	17.5	21.3	18.53
	3-13	16.43	20.65	17.46	17.3	21.59	18.6
	50-58	18.92	25.36	22.02			
N/400-BaCl ₂	5-13	14.67	17.12	15.28	15.35	22.88	17.23
	115-120	18.26	25.36	20.03			
	5-15	13.36	16.01	14.02			
	85-95	18.8	26.91	20.85	15.39	23.03	17.27
N/2500-AlCl ₃	8-13	16.42	23.99	18.28	12.4	16.56	13.46
	43-50	21.47	28.07	21.9			
	7-12	16.93	23.42	18.54	12.09	16.87	13.27
	44-49	21.76	29.67	23.73			
N/3000-AlCl ₃	3-8	10.85	16.67	12.19			
	19-22	15.68	20.72	16.91	11.54	13.96	12.11
	30-34	17.06	22.78	18.47			

Palmitic Acid Sol.

Palmitic acid sol has been prepared as described below 50 C.c. of a saturated solution of palmitic acid in alcohol were added slowly to 500 c.c of warm water. It was kept overnight when some acid was coagulated and floated above. The clear sol was pipetted out for experiments. The sol became coarser after a few days. Table V and Fig. 3 illustrate the results.

FIG. 3.
As₂S₃ and palmitic acid sols

Curves 1 and 2 refer respectively to $As_2S_3 + N/7-KCl$ and palmitic acid + $N/800-AlCl_3$
O means C. V. after coagulation

FIG. 4.
V₂O₅ sol.

Curves 1-3 refer respectively to $N/1500-BaCl_2$, $N/1000-AlCl_3$ and $N/15-KCl$.
O means C. V. after coagulation.

TABLE V.

Electrolyte	Time after mixing.	Before coagulation			After coagulation.		
		$V_{\frac{1}{2}}$	$V_{\frac{1}{4}}$	V	$V_{\frac{1}{2}}$	$V_{\frac{1}{4}}$	V.
Water		7.643	10.63	8.38			
N/2-KCl	2-9 min	15.03	24.31	17.32	16.03	24.3	18.7
	67-72	18.03	28.54	20.65			
	2-12	15.11	23.1	17.08			
	61-71	17.95	28.64	20.6			

TABLE V (contd.).

Electrolyte.	Time after mixing.	Before coagulation.			After coagulation.		
		$V_{\frac{1}{8}}$.	$V_{\frac{1}{2}}$.	V .	$V_{\frac{1}{8}}$.	$V_{\frac{1}{2}}$.	V .
$N/100\text{-BaCl}_2$	2-7	11-47	16-08	12-6			
	60-69	17-46	23-36	18-92	10-82	15-00	11-86
	126-128	16-92	23-69	18-61			
$N/800\text{-AlCl}_3$	2-7	16-03	27-68	18-94			
	17-21	21-04	31-39	23-63			
	24-26	22-22	31-9	24-63			
	36-39	25-36	35-32	27-85			
	56-59	26-02	34-04	28-02			
	3-8	16-32	27-35	19-07			
	18-24	21-26	24-73	22-12	19-1	21-3	19-6
60-66	25-68	34-7	27-93				

Vanadium Pentoxide Sol.

Ammonium vanadate (5 g.) was triturated in a mortar with a few drops of hydrochloric acid. The red precipitate, thus obtained, was washed continuously on a Buchner filter until the filtrate assumed a red colour. The precipitate was washed further and the filtrate collected and transferred to a bottle and stirred with 200 c.c. of water. Within a few hours, a dark red colloidal solution was obtained which was fairly clear to transmitted light. Results are given in Table VI and illustrated in Fig. 4.

TABLE VI.

Electrolyte.	Time after mixing.	Before coagulation.			After coagulation.		
		$V_{\frac{1}{8}}$.	$V_{\frac{1}{2}}$.	V .	$V_{\frac{1}{8}}$.	$V_{\frac{1}{2}}$.	V .
Water		23-29	45-11	28-73			
$N/15\text{-KCl}$	2-6 min.	25-62	43-35	30-05			
	14-18	31-39	45-13	34-82	25-19	43-08	29-64
	27-30	32-39	45-8	35-68			
	47-49	33-34	46-7	36-68			
$N/1500\text{-BaCl}_2$	1-6	33-68	40-98	36-25			
	11-15	37-4	43-57	38-94	33-85	43-58	36-27
	20-25	51-45	62-85	52-3			
	1-3	34-4	42-48	36-42			
	9-13	37-33	43-98	38-98	33-36	42-22	35-57
	10-23	50-71	61-8	53-46			
28-31	51-33	61-59	53-88				
$N/1000\text{-AlCl}_3$	1-5	34-24	42-86	36-39			
	9-16	34-9	44-5	37-26			
	20-23	36-34	45-64	38-66	30-48	45-27	34-17
	31-36	40-46	49-45	42-7			
	44-48	40-93	51-48	43-56			

Tungstic Acid Hydrosol.

From a solution of sodium tungstate, the oxide was precipitated by the action of hot concentrated HCl. The precipitate, so obtained, was filtered, washed with moderately dilute hydrochloric acid 3 or 4 times and once again with hot distilled water. With further washing the precipitate became peptised. The precipitate was then transferred to a bottle and suspended in water when it formed a sol. The peptised sol was dialysed in collodion sacs for a week with frequent changes of water and then electro-dialysed for three days. Finally the sol was deposited by the current on the membrane and the supernatant water decanted off. The residue was now peptised with conductivity water and stocked in a bottle. The sol was coarsely dispersed and the larger particles settled down in a few days. Experiments were performed with portions of the sol pipetted out. The results are given in table VII and Fig. 5.

FIG. 5.

Tungstic acid sol.

Curves 1 and 2 refer respectively to $N/25\text{-KCl}$ and $N/1000\text{-BaCl}_2$.
 O means C. V. after coagulation.

TABLE VII.

Electrolyte.	Time after mixing.	Before coagulation.			After coagulation.		
		$V_{\frac{1}{2}}$.	$V_{\frac{1}{3}}$.	V .	$V_{\frac{1}{2}}$.	$V_{\frac{1}{3}}$.	V .
Water		21.26	31.9	23.92			
N/20-KCl	2-7 min.	22.65	31.2	24.78	22.85	28.96	24.4
	14-19	25.19	31.88	26.76			
	25-33	26.53	32.51	28.02			
N/25-KCl	2-8	30.56	42.16	33.46	26.9	35.5	29.08
	14-19	34.31	42.18	36.28			
	27-35	36.09	48.39	39.15			
	44-49	37.11	48.35	39.92			
N/1000-BaCl ₂	2-5	14.16	19.33	15.45	12.99	18.2	14.3
	10-15	16.29	21.33	17.54			
	20-24	20.62	24.07	21.46			
	32-46	21.18	24.26	21.93			

DISCUSSION.

The experimental results might be briefly summarised as follows :

(1) With arsenious sulphide hydrosol and potassium chloride, the c.v. increases with time to a value greater than the initial c.v. of the pure colloid. With barium chloride and aluminium chloride, though the c.v. is lower than that of the pure colloid, the c.v. here also increases with time in presence of a definite concentration of the electrolytes (*cf.* Fig. 2).

(2) With palmitic acid sol and the vanadium pentoxide hydrosol, the c.v. continually increases with time and is always higher than the initial c.v. of the pure colloid in presence of all the electrolytes. The initial c.v. of the palmitic acid sol is 8.38×10^{-5} cm./sec. per volt/cm., whereas that of the vanadium pentoxide hydrosol is 28.7×10^{-5} cm./sec. per volt/cm. (*cf.* Fig. 3 and 4).

(3) With tungstic acid sol also, the c.v. increases with time and is greater than that of the pure colloid with potassium chloride; in presence of barium chloride, the c.v. is lower than the initial value but as aggregation proceeds, it increases with time (*cf.* Fig. 5).

(4) The c.v. of particles of a partially coagulated sol is lower than that of the sol before coagulation (*cf.* Fig. 2—5 and Tables III—VII).

(5) The c.v. of a colloid in presence of an electrolyte is smaller after the sol is centrifuged (*cf.* Table III; *cf.* also Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 431).

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(6) If the c.v. of the large particles, which have settled during coagulation, be measured, being thoroughly shaken with the partially coagulated supernatant fluid, then it is found to be the same as that of the partially coagulated sol (*cf.* Table III). Results on points (4), (5) and (6) are tabulated below for the sake of clarity.

TABLE VIII.

Sol.	Electrolyte.	Cataphoretic velocity	
		Before coagulation.	After coagulation.
Arsenious sulphide	N/6-KCl	43.75	35.2
		45.78	33.54
		44.39	34.96 36.2*
	N/7-KCl	43.02	39.68
		43.95	39.95
		43.95	40.97
		43.6	39.6
	N/8-KCl	49.77	47.67
	N/300-BaCl ₂	21.06	17.54
		21.98	17.67
	N/350 "	21.01	18.53
		22.02	18.6
	N/400 "	20.03	17.23
		20.85	17.27
	N/1500-AlCl ₃	23.09	13.46
23.73		13.27	
18.47		12.13	
Vanadium pentoxide	N/15-KCl	36.68	29.64
	N/1500-BaCl ₂	53.3	36.27
		53.88	35.57
N/1000-AlCl ₃	43.66	34.17	
Tungstic acid	N/20-KCl	28.02	24.4
	N/25 "	39.92	29.08
	N/1000-BaCl ₂	21.93	14.3
Palmitic acid	N/2-KCl	20.65	18.7
	N/100-BaCl ₂	18.61	11.86
	N/800-AlCl ₃	27.93	19.6

* Supernatant coagulated sol thoroughly shaken with the original precipitate and c.v. measured.

These results are rather peculiar and they cannot be explained on the basis of any of the theories referred to. The outstanding facts that require to be explained, are :

(i) The increase of c.v. of a colloid with time in presence of an electrolyte at a concentration which produces an appreciable rate of coagulation.

(ii) That the increase in c.v. is due to the aggregation of the colloidal particles and not due to adsorption of ions of similar charge is evident from the fact that with salts having polyvalent cations of very low concentrations where the concentrations of anions are very small, the c.v. sometimes increases to a much greater extent than it does with uni-univalent salts.

Dependence of c.v. on Size, Shape and Ionic Strength.

According to the usual cataphoretic equation

$$V = \frac{\xi DX}{4\pi\eta} \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

where V is the cataphoretic velocity in cm. per volt/cm., ξ , the electro-kinetic potential, D , the dielectric constant, X , the potential gradient in volts/cm., and η , the viscosity, the velocity should be independent of the size and shape of the particle and ξ , the electro-kinetic potential should determine the mobility. Debye and Hückel (*Physikal. Z.*, 1924, 25, 49) on the other hand have deduced the relation

$$V = c. \frac{DX\xi}{\eta} \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

where c , the constant, varies with the shape of the particle. In the case of a spherical particle, c is equal to $1/6\pi$, while for a cylinder it is $1/4\pi$. Henry (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1931, A, 133, 106) further points out that the value of the constant is $1/4\pi$, when the cylinder is placed axially to the applied field, but if it be placed broadside, c is $1/8\pi$. Moreover, the Debye equation is found by Henry to be true for spheres only when the electrical conductivity of the particle is identical with that of the medium. He also finds that in this case, the c. v. would depend on the shape of the particle. For an insulated particle, however, the Helmholtz-Smoluchowski equation is valid. Henry's actual

equation is

$$u = \frac{3\mu}{2\mu + \mu'} \cdot \frac{DX\xi}{6\pi\eta} \quad \dots \quad (iii)$$

He states "for an insulating sphere $\eta' = 0$ and $u = \frac{DX\xi}{4\pi\eta}$ in agreement with Smoluchowski's result, which is thus confirmed for a rigid spherical insulating particle subject to his four restrictions." μ and μ' are the specific conductances of the medium and the particle respectively and u , the mobility. In such a case, therefore, the cataphoretic velocity is independent of the shape and size of the particles. Henry (*loc. cit.*) further deduces the equation

$$V = \frac{X\sigma}{K} \cdot \frac{Ka}{1+Ka} \cdot (Ka) \quad \dots \quad (iv)$$

where V = mobility, σ = density of charge, a = radius of the colloidal particle, X = applied field and

$$K^2 = \frac{4\pi Ne^2}{1000DkT} \cdot \sum \gamma_i z_i^2$$

N is the Avogadro number, D , the dielectric constant, k the Boltzmann constant, T the absolute temperature, e , the charge of the electron in c. G. s. units and γ_i , the concentration per litre and z_i , the valency of the i th type.

To quote Henry again "we find that for values of Ka not less than 300, Smoluchowski's equation should hold to within 1%. For smaller values of Ka , if (Ka) diminishes towards the value $\frac{2}{3}$, until values of Ka about 0.5, Hückel's equation in turn becomes valid to within 1%. Provisionally, however, it may be inferred that particles in colloidal solutions will almost always lie in the region within which the cataphoretic velocity varies with the size but that droplets in emulsions and other suspended particles of microscopic size (as distinct from ultramicroscopic) should provide material for the experimental verification of Smoluchowski's equation." Henry (*loc. cit.*) gives the following table, showing the limits of diameter and of thickness of the ion atmosphere within which the Smoluchowski and Hückel equations are valid.

TABLE IX

(From Henry, *loc. cit.*) .

Electrolyte.	Conc. $f(N)$.	K at 20° in cm^{-1} .	τ/K in μ .	Diameters.	
				S.	H.
Pure water		1.0×10^4	1.0	600	1.0
Uni-univalent	10^{-5}	1.0×10^5	0.1	60	0.1
	10^{-3}	1.0×10^6	0.01	6.0	0.01
	10^{-1}	1.0×10^7	0.0001	0.6	0.001
Uni-bivalent	10^{-5}	1.8×10^5	0.056	34	0.056
	10^{-1}	1.8×10^7	0.00056	0.34	0.00056
Bi-valent	10^{-5}	2.1×10^5	0.048	29	0.048
	10^{-1}	2.1×10^7	0.00048	0.29	0.00048

Muller (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, **35**, 289) and Mooney (*ibid.*, 1931, **35**, 331) have attempted to explain the observations of Mooney (*loc. cit.*) as follows:

By applying the interionic attraction theory of Debye to colloidal particles Muller postulates that

$$\xi = \frac{4\pi\epsilon}{D} \cdot \frac{\tau}{K} \cdot \frac{Ka}{1 + Ka} \quad \dots \quad (v)$$

and comparing it with the equation

$$\xi = \frac{4\pi\epsilon}{D} \cdot d \quad \dots \quad (vi)$$

where d is the thickness of the double layer and the other symbols have the same meaning as in equations (ii) and (iv), he gets the relation

$$d = \frac{\tau}{K} \cdot \frac{Ka}{1 + Ka} \quad (vii)$$

This formula shows that in general, the thickness of the double layer depends on the radius of the particle. This dependence of d on radius will manifest itself if Ka is small (*cf.* Henry, *loc. cit.*). Further when Ka is very large compared to unity, the cataphoretic velocity should become independent of the radius—conclusions which are similar to those drawn by Henry (*loc. cit.*). Mooney's experimental results are considered by Muller to agree with these conclusions, as large particles (where Ka is very large compared to unity) of nearly equal size having the most diverse shapes, move with a velocity in agreement with the theory of Smoluchowski, whenever the chemical constitution of the surface of the different particles is the same.

This theory is also considered to account for the observation of Mooney (*loc. cit.*) that with the addition of an electrolyte, the postulated increase in c. v. with increase in size, shifts to smaller radii and Abramsohn's observations that the c. v. of particles of microscopic size (1μ to 10μ approx.) are independent of the size for Ka now becomes sufficiently large. According to equation (vi) at a concentration of the electrolyte greater than 0.001 normal, particles of and above microscopic size (1μ to 10μ) should never show a variation of c. v. with size. Actually, however, we have found that such a variation occurs even for larger particles in solutions containing stronger electrolyte concentrations.

The limits of concentrations were from 0.001 N to 0.2 N . It follows from Table IX, given above that aggregates at such electrolyte concentrations should have a constant c. v. independent of size and shape and obey the Smoluchowski equation. Further, at such high ionic strengths, the c. v. should be small as the effective thickness of the ionic atmosphere must be small. Also, as the aggregation proceeds the shape should approximate a sphere assuming a chaotic arrangement of the primary particles and the c. v. should diminish. The observed increase in c. v. on aggregation contradicts all these deductions.

Considering the effect of an increase of the ionic strength it follows from the applications of the Debye-Hückel theory of strong electrolytes that the thickness of the double layer, or, of the ion atmosphere must diminish and the c. v. must decrease. But instead of a decrease, an increase has often been observed under such circumstances (Mukherjee, et al *loc. cit.*)

Another contradiction is afforded by the observation that the percentage increase in c. v. with time is greater in the case of the electrolytes having polyvalent precipitating ions which have a lower ionic strength. It follows from equations (iv) and (v) on the other hand, that the variation in c. v. with increase in the electrolyte concentration should diminish as the ionic strength diminishes, if the comparison is restricted to the aggregation of the same set of particles (Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*). It is obvious that all these theories ignore the part played by the specific character of the surface and the adsorption of ions.

The general picture of the changes brought about by the addition of an electrolyte and the consequent aggregation of the particles in the equilibrium distribution of ions in the double layer surrounding

the primary particles have been visualised before (Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*). These changes can be stated as follows in detail:

(a) Changes in the distribution of the ions in the double layer surrounding the primary particles which may affect the primarily adsorbed, the electrically adsorbed ions, and those in the mobile layer.

(b) Rearrangement of the above distribution resulting from the aggregation of the colloidal particles (assuming no change in the surface of the primary particles forming the aggregate) which involves a diminution in the capacity. The aggregation may also involve an increase in the surface density of the charge in the neighbourhood of the surface of aggregation.

(c) A net diminution in the interface may result from the coalescence at the particular spots of the aggregating particles. This would increase the surface density of the charge and the potential if the fixed layer of adsorbed ions is not affected by coalescence. On the other hand the fixed adsorbed ions at such places with their mobile particles may be set free as a result of the coalescence. Perhaps, this happens when precipitation takes place and with which is associated the sudden drop in the potential.

(d) An entrainment of ions serving as links between the primary particles, which unite them into the aggregate, may also happen.

The considerations advanced above have an important bearing on problems in several branches of science, *e.g.*, the formation of soil aggregates. It has been observed that the effect of (a) is often to increase the c. v. if the initial density of the charge of the colloid is low, specially with univalent coagulating ions (*cf.* Figs. 2, 4, 5 and Table V) and sometimes even with divalent or trivalent coagulating ions (*cf.* Fig. 4 and Table V). With divalent or trivalent precipitating cations, the electrical adsorption should predominate. The c. v. would diminish on the addition of the electrolyte but it has been observed (*vide* Figs. 2, 3, 4, 5) that the c. v. increases with aggregation in this case also. Moreover, the c. v. on the addition of electrolytes with divalent and trivalent cations is in several instances (*vide* Tables III to VIII) greater than that of the pure colloid. These observations dispose of the arguments often advanced (Kruyt and Willizen, *Kolloid Z.*, 1928, **44**, 22) to explain away the high coagulating potentials observed with univalent coagulating ions. It is maintained that there is a critical coagulating potential in the case of electrolytes

which coagulate at low concentrations and that the higher potential observed with univalent coagulating ions is an exception arising out of the adsorption of ions of same sign or out of the decrease of the dielectric constant at such high concentrations. This argument also overlooks the higher potential itself, as the stability is assumed to be directly determined by the potential, no matter what the causal factors are. In several instances, the percentage increase in c. v. is greater for the bi- or trivalent than with the univalent precipitating ions. The magnitude of the change in c. v. appears to depend on the cation and on the sol. It is possible that the polyvalent cations, which are known to produce coagula in which the primary particles are more firmly bound, bring the surfaces of the primary particles in closer contact and hence enhance the potential.

Apart from these considerations, there might be an increase in the c. v. due to endosmosis set up in the cell as a result of the net work structure of the coagula in the cell. But these and other considerations await further experimental results before any definite conclusion as to the effect it produces can be arrived at.

SUMMARY.

1. It has been shown that the c. v. of a colloid increases with time, *i.e.*, with the process of aggregation of the colloidal particles in presence of an electrolyte.
2. This effect, *i.e.*, the increase in c. v. with time, is more marked, the higher the valency of the precipitating ions. Sometimes the c. v. rises to a much higher value than that of the colloid itself with di- or trivalent precipitating ions.
3. The c. v. of the supernatant suspension of a colloid after partial coagulation is less than that of the colloid before coagulation.
4. The c. v. of the coagula (in the case of As_2S_3 sol) is the same as that of the supernatant suspension of the colloid after coagulation.
5. These results are not in accord with the theories of cataphoresis as developed by Helmholtz, Smoluchowski, Debye and Hückel and Henry and Mooney. A tentative suggestion based on the considerations of Mukherjee's theory of ion adsorption and of the aggregation of the colloidal particles has been advanced.